

Birds in everyday life and art in Bulgaria (Thracian and Roman periods)

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Abstract: This paper presents and analyses for the first time all data on the presence of birds (bone finds; 26 sites; 84 species/genera) and their images in the art works (34 sites; 40 species/genera) from monuments of the ancient Thracian and Roman lands in Bulgaria (2200 BC – 4th c. AD), their utilisation and importance. Data of a total of 96 taxa of 29 families and 18 orders are presented.

Different aspects of the use of birds have been considered: hunting, domestication, falconry, decorative faunisation, including secondary use (as a source of bone material for the production of tools and adornments). The main groups of birds (waterfowl, eagles, pigeons, peacocks, etc.) and their symbolic mythological significance are presented.

The images of some monuments represent exotic birds (purple swamphen, Egyptian goose, ring-necked parakeet, helmeted guineafowl, Abyssinian lovebird, African green pigeon, spur-winged goose) which are now spread beyond the former Roman Empire (and Bulgarian) lands, mainly in East Africa. Their present ranges overlap only in the region of East Africa. They confirm ancient trans-Saharan Roman-“Ethiopian” contacts.

Key words: Birds in antiquity, ancient art, birds-man interrelations, Late Holocene birds, ornithoarchaeology

Introduction

Currently, the human-bird interactions in the Thracian (and Roman) period in Bulgaria have not been studied in details. Only scattered and fragmentary data exist. Ornithoarchaeological information is much more abundant. The aim of this paper is to evaluate the role of birds in the spiritual (especially in the /visual/ art) and everyday life of the Thracians and Romans.

Now it is well accepted, that Thrace was under the influence of the Mycenaean civilisation after the last phase of the Bronze Age. In Thrace existed some state entities which, regardless of the local differences, were fundamentally similar to the Mycenaean (Tacheva-Hitova, 1976). In the regions of Western and Eastern Bulgaria, in the interior of the country, some Thracian state formations existed already during the second half of the 2nd millennium BC (Velkov, 1979).

The Thracian art in Bulgaria has been subject of numerous investigations and interpretations so

far. The abundant archaeological records of thousands of monuments from the Thracian period throughout Bulgarian lands (including all neighbouring countries) provide an excellent heritage and make it the richest art heritage of that period (15th c. BC – 6th c. AD) in Europe and in the world (Dimitrov, 1978a, b; Bozhkov, 1988, 1993).

Overall, among the most exhaustive studies on Thracian art are those of Filov (1918), Tsoncheva (1971), Venedikov, Gerasimov (1974), Lazarov (1990) on the Thracian pottery, Dimitrov (1991), etc.

Birds alone in the ancient Thracian and Roman lands of Bulgaria have not been a subject of special studies until present, although some studies on the fauna of ancient Thrace, as reflected in the ancient literature, exist (Velkov, 1956 a, b). The only research on the birds during the Roman period of Bulgaria was published by Boev (2006), where data on 85 avian taxa were presented.

In the last two decades, the ornithoarchaeological exploration of several dozens of monuments of Thracian (and early Roman) periods revealed interesting details of exploitation of birds by the ancient population in the Bulgarian lands.

Material and Methods

The Thracian period in the history of the Bulgarian lands covers the time from approximately 2200 BC – 2nd c. BC (Velkov, 1979). In the present study we discuss all preserved images (pictures, bas-reliefs, statuettes, sculptures, etc.) of birds, found only in the present (since 1945) Bulgarian lands, although former Thrace included parts of present Southern Bulgaria, Westernmost Turkey and Eastern Greece (Velkov, 1979). The numerous archaeological finds in the former lands of the Thracians from the neighbouring countries remain out of the scope of this paper.

The subfossil records of the Late Holocene birds of the Late Bronze and Iron Ages and the Early Antiquity are presented in brief, as a number of special publications present this matter in more detail.

The “eagle-griffons”, “lion-griffons”, “horse-roosters” (hippaletrions) and other fantastic creatures are intentionally omitted from this research. Their mythological and art significance are not taken into account, but they are listed as types only for comparison purposes. Although Kovachev, Sirakov (2016) state that modern scientists still argue about the kind of bird, depicted as a hippaletrion, i. e. junglefowl (rooster), vulture or (?) griffon, here we have to remind that the griffon is not a real animal species. It is a mythological creature and we could firmly accept that the hind part of the hippaletrion represents the hind part of the body of a rooster. The same applies for the discussed by Kovachev and Sirakov (2016) rhyton of Taneva mound from the Sliven District. In addition, the numerous “eagle-griffons” are not accepted and discussed as eagles.

List of the archaeological monuments with bird bone remains from the Thracian/Roman period in Bulgaria (Table 1):

Abritus
Arbanas
Armira
Bagachina
Chavdarova Cheshma
Ezero
Filipovska Cave – 2*

Galabovo
Gledachevo
Golyamata Peshtera Cave
Kabile
Kostinbrod
Malak Preslavets – 2
Nicopolis-ad-Istrum
Novae
Orphey
Peshterata na strelite
Radnevo
Ratiaria
Serdica
Shipka
Sozopol
Urdoviza
Yassa-Tepe
Zelenigradska Cave

List of the archaeological monuments with bird images from the Thracian/Roman period in Bulgaria (Table 1):

Armira
Borovo
Chernozem
Dolna Koznitsa
Dragodan
Durostorum (pr. Silistra)
Duvanli
Galiche
Garchinovo
Garescus (pr. Sandanski)
Ginina Mound, Sveshtari
Kabile
Kralevo
Letnitsa
Magurata Cave
Malomirovo
Marcianopolis
Morozovo (pr. Gorno Tserkovishte)
Mramor Mound, Panagyurishte
Nesebar
Oescus
Orsoya
Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)
Rila Monastery
Rogozen
Seuthopolis
Shekerdzha Mound, Kamen
Shipka
Sofia
Sozopol
Starosel
Sveta Sofia Church
Tazha
Varbitsa

* “Filipovska Cave – 2” and “Malak Preslavets – 2” are listed as they appeared in the original publications.

General characteristics of the Thracian art and its expressive significance

As known, the Thracians did not have their own writing system. On certain occasions they used Ancient Greek writing, for example for the inscriptions on their vessels, often decorated with images of animals, including fine birds. It is notable, that the introduction of elements of the Hellenic iconography coincides with the first attempts for wider use of the Hellenic alphabet and language in the superscripts of the Thracian objects. According to Fol (1975), the art in Thrace was “aristocratic” in the 6th c. BC and after. The social fundament of the Thracian art led it to a rapid decline in times of social-political turbulences (Fol et al., 1993). These authors determine the Thracian art as “geometric” in the 8th – 7th c. BC. According to Venedikov (1981), the geometric art and the animal ornaments appear in the western Thracian regions in the 7th and 6th c. BC.

Thracian art treats the balance between one or another natural force, as well as that between man and nature, as opposed to the Hellenics, whose principles compare the relationship between human beings or those between humans and deities. From this point of view, two distinctly different systems are distinguished, which suggests radically different symbolic structures. In fact, the language of art remains the only authentic “Thracian” language.

During the Late Iron Age the Thracian art has its achievements in the tomb architecture (the tombs in Kazanlak, Sveshtari), secular buildings, toreutics (the treasures of Letnitsa, Lukovit, Borovo, Rogozen), decorations for horse ammunition (Brezovo, Bukyovtsi, Oryahovo, Orizovo), etc. (Fol et al., 1993).

In general, the Thracian culture reaches its peak in the 6th c. BC. It is the time of the great golden and silver treasures made to please the aristocracy (Venedikov, 1982).

The zoomorphism of the Thracian art

The art of the Thracians is possibly the most “zoomorphic” among the ancient cultures of Europe. It is a representation of natural powers and gods with the qualities and peculiarities of animals. The zoomorphism (the so-called “animal style” of Scythians) is a result of the early religious concepts that convey the meaning of the gods using animal style. This stage of the zoomorphic pantheon precedes the stage of the anthropomorphic divine images.

The lands of the ancient Thracians, situated in the south-eastern corner of Europe, during the whole Holocene is the region with the richest biodiversity

Fig. 1. Goose's head from the Chernozem Village (Plovdiv Region; 2nd half of 5th c. BC). After Kisyov (2005).

Fig. 2. Swans of the bronze pitcher-rython of the Borovo treasure (Ruse Region; 4th c. BC). After Ivanov (1975).

of the continent, including the most abundant (and favourable) faunal resources to man (sea coasts, river estuaries, lagoons, coastal and inland lakes, swamps and marshes, alpine landscapes and vast plains, rock massifs, gorges, dense broad-lived and coniferous forests, meadows, steppes and many others).

It is assumed that zoomorphism is one of the “codes” of mythology, folklore, epos and pictorial art, through which particular type of texts are created, in which animals play a major role. In the early stages of art development, the animal code better corresponds to the iconography inherited from the “geometric” era. Therefore, zoomorphism is inherent not of thinking (content) but of expression, and it is a problem of pictorial language (Fol et al., 1993). The “animal motif”, treated realistically, prevails in the Thracian art. The “animal style” of Thracian toreutics is a peculiar expression of the aesthetics of the Thracians (Vaklinov, 1973).

Like the other iconic signs, the zoomorphs have no definite meaning outside the given context. Therefore, it is necessary to determine with which other codes the zoomorphic link is connected to.

Fig. 3. Horned eagle of the Rogozen treasure (Rogozen Village, Vratsa Region; 2nd half of 4th c. BC). After Nikolov (1987).

This makes it possible to understand the particular meaning of an animal in the pictorial narrative. In the “animal style” of Thrace, there are three groups of fauna: predators (lion, panther, bear, dog, wolf), herbivores (deer, horse, wild boar) and birds (most often predatory and waterfowl; Figs. 1, 2.).

According to Venedikov (1974b), such a „zoological” subject-matter appears from the East in the 6th c. BC, although based on mythical creatures, such as horned lion, lion-griffon, horned eagle (Fig. 3), horse-roosters, etc.

The zoomorphic decoration takes place either as a shaping of the entire object or part of it as a figure of an (vertebrate) animal. In the Late Bronze Age, the image of a water bird is most commonly used (Fol et al., 1993). Among them, often we find images of pond ducks, geese, swans, etc.

Zoomorphism develops further during the

Fig. 4. “Eagle” with beaked fish and rabbit in the claws of the Rogozen treasure (Rogozen Village, Vratsa Region; 2nd half of 4th c. BC) After Fol. et. al. (1988).

Early Iron Age, when heels of the cult axes, amulets or forehead plates are decorated with or shaped as the figures of domestic animals: ram, goat, bull. The bird is also among the main symbols. This increased interest in animal figures and their individual parts (mostly the head) are embodied using a new material – the bronze. Small statuettes are also produced, which may be decorated with cult or social attributes. The animal figures are still geometrically stylised: the body is represented as a prism, the head as a “reel”, the eyes are circles and the back becomes a hemisphere. This geometric (stereometric, in fact) style is typical of the art of Middle and South-eastern Europe, the Caucasus and Iran, and includes Thracian art culture in the same international community. In the Late Bronze Age, there is some resemblance to the decorative repertoire of Mycenaean art (Fol et al., 1993). Fol et al. (1993) summarise, that since the end of the Late Bronze Age, the ornamental fund includes spirals, volutes (spiral ornaments), concentric circles with centre point meanders, diamonds and triangles (sometimes shaded), points and semicircles. Such geometrical ornaments are preserved from as early as the 6th c. BC, when only the decoration system changes. In many monuments of the Roman period we find a number of complex ornaments, enclosing images of birds in the ancient mosaics, for example.

Ornithomorphic symbols in the Thracian art

Zoomorphic symbolism also enters the political terminology of the ancient world. Thus, in the emblematic group of the eagle with beaked fish and hare in the claws (Fig. 4), it is coded by the animal classifiers of the elements of the Achemenian

Fig. 5. Eagle's head from the Tomb of the Seuthes III from the Golyama Kosmatka Mound near town of Shipka (Stara Zagora Region; 2nd half of 4th c. BC). After: <https://www.google.bg/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=images&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwj5jMOz7b7QAhUJkRQKHegaA0oQjRwIBw&url=https://www.pinterest.com/pin/455004368580109057/?psig=AFQjCNFLks0-f64TyjM5q-EXt7mSybLjXA&ust=1479974585173765>

political formula: “Bring Me Water and Land” by which the victor-king turns to the defeated ruler (Fol et al., 1993). The same bird (“eagle”) is represented in the Rogozen treasure (Nikolov et al., 1986, 1987), Seuthopolis (Tsoncheva, 1971), Shipka (Agre, 2006; Marazov, 2010; Fig. 5), Dragodan (Teodosiev, Manov, 1993), Armira (Mladenova, 1991), Nicopolis ad Nestum (Popova-Moroz, 1987) and many other sites (Table 1). According to Popova-Moroz (1987) the pigeons and peafowls in front of the vine kylixes symbolise the communion. The water birds (and birds with beaked fish) symbolise the new person's state after the conversion to Christianity.

The “eagle” of the treasure of Letnitsa (Venedikov, 1996) is actually a gryffon, rather than

an eagle (Fig. 6). The oldest monument in Bulgaria representing the Mother of the gods with the raptor bird (with the appearance of an “eagle” again) in Thrace, is the handle of a bronze mirror from the Chukurka Village near Aytos (Burgas Region from the end of the 6th c. BC; Venedikov, 1992).

The main animal images of the previous period are later replaced by the victim or prey. The animal images and scenes become a means of expressing mythological and ideological ideas. Among the archaeologists and culturologists there is no doubt about the contribution of the Achaemenid art to iconography of animal style.

“Bird” as a generalised image is present in numerous artworks at many Thracian sites. Usually the “bird” is not a raptor, wader, owl, duck/swan, swan, crane, etc. It is often depicted as a “birdie”, and a good example for it are the two bird images of a phalera plate of Galiche Village (Filov, Velkov 1919-1920; Fig. 7).

Birds on the Balkans, in Bulgaria and the former Thracian/ Roman lands

The recent avifauna of the Balkan Peninsula numbers circa 516 species (Michev et al., 2013), while the bird fauna of Bulgaria alone includes 420 species (Ivanov et al., 2015). On the other hand, the ornithoarchaeological data of the Thracian period from Bulgaria cover 84 species/genera (Boev, 1993, 1996a,

Fig. 6. Griffon, attacking a deer of the treasure of Letnitsa (Lovech Region; 2nd half of 4th c. BC). After: https://www.google.bg/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=images&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwiU_e381azQAHWBvBQKHaxtBaYQjRwIBw&url=http://trakite.info/traki-sakrovishhta/sakrovishhte-letnica.html&psig=AFQjCNHF5OIL85RUPCfYA-Ec4kehFZ7IA&ust=1479364661087056

1996b, 1997a, 1997b, 1999, 2004, 2006; Table 1). These subfossil remains of birds have been found at 27 archaeological sites: in present Southern Bulgaria – Kabile (Boev, Ribarov, 1993), Shipka (Boev, 1999), Urdoviza (Boev, Ribarov, 1990), Sozopol (Boev, 1995), Galabovo (Boev, 2004), Radnevo (Boev, 2004), Yassa-Tepe (Ribarov, Boev, 1990), Gledachevo (Boev, 1999, 2006), Zelenigradska Cave (Boev, 2001, 2006), Filipovska Cave – 2 (Boev, 2001, 2006), Golyamata Peshtera Cave near Kyustendil (Boev, 1999), Serdica

(Boev, 2017a) and Chavdarova Cheshma (Boev, 2017b); and in Northern Bulgaria – Bagachina (Boev, 1996b, 1999), Nicopolis-ad-Istrum (Boev, 1991, 2006; Boev, Beech, 2007), Abritus (Boev, 2006), Ratiaria (Iliev et al., 1993; Boev, 2006), Malak Preslavets – 2 (Boev, 2006), Ezero (Ivanov, Vasilev, 1979) and Novae (Schram, 1975, 1979; Walushevsk-Bubien, Krupska, 1983; Bartosiewicz, Choyke, 1991). Most of these 84 species/genera represent game fowl, waterfowl and other hunting and domestic birds (Table 1).

Importance of birds for ancient Thracians and Romans

It is well known that different species of birds have different ethnological importance. Always Usually the domestic birds are the most important among the birds in the everyday life (Fig. 8), followed by the large game birds.

Both groups (domestic and game) have been used as a source of meat, eggs, bones, feathers, down, etc. (s. c. “primary utilisation”). Some other aspects of the utilisation of birds in the Thracian period (Late Bronze Age to Iron Age and the Antiquity) are listed by Boev (2011). In the sunken settlement of Urdoviza (near Kiten, Burgas Region) are found three long hollow wing bones of the Great white pelican (*Pelecanus onocrotalus*), which have been cut and wound up as a part of a device for blowing or sucking/infusion (Boev, Ribarov, 1990; Boev 2011; Fig. 9).

In the settlement of Bagachina (near Rasovo Village, Montana Region) from the Early Iron Age, a bone ring of the diaphysis of the humeral bone of the wing of a domestic goose (*Anser anser domestica*) are found (Boev, 2011). In Apolonia a flute of long bones of birds have been found in 2007 (Golemanov, 2012).

Fig. 7. Generalised “bird” image of the phalera plate of Galiche Village (Vratsa Region) (2nd-1st c. BC). After: https://www.google.bg/search?q=%D1%84%D0%B0%D0%BB%D0%B5%D1%80%D0%B0%D1%82%D0%B0+%D0%BE%D1%82+%D0%B3%D0%B0%D0%BB%D0%B8%D1%87%D0%B5&dcr=0&tbm=isch&source=iu&ictx=1&fir=y0kfj6VlgI7wLM%253A%252CQuQ4g7UmxRFiM%252C_&usg=__tgmD82SFHQwMVT3XflbRQ0myTto%3D&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwivzqDegL7ZAhWKqaQKHV_JBZsQ9QEIRDAF#imgsrc=y0kfj6VlgI7wLM:

Fig. 8. Indian peafowl (*Pavo cristatus*) from the Roman mosaic of the Bishop Basilica in Plovdiv (5-6th c. BC). After: https://www.google.bg/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&resrc=s&source=images&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwifwuKDhZzQAWhWDuxQKHfX4C0gQjRwiBw&url=http://www.dnevnik.bg/razvlechenie/2015/12/15/2670438_proektut_za_episkopskata_bazilika_dobavia_oshte_edin/?ref=id&bvml=bv.138169073,d.d24&psig=AFQjCNG_F9Nhb3wmsr-Ih2vEKnP-1jceUg&ust=1478793330707090

Table 1. Avian records (bone remains, art images) in Thracian/Roman monuments of Bulgaria

No	Taxa	Bird bone remains			Bird images	
		Site	Source	Site	Source	
ANSERIFORMES						
Anatidae						
1	<i>Cygnus cygnus</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)		Ivanov (1975), Venedikov (1992)	
		Novae	Schramm (1975)	Borovo		
2	<i>Cygnus olor</i>	Novae	Bartosiewicz, Choyke (1991)	Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)	
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
3	<i>Cygnus</i> sp.			Varbitsa	Filov (1934)	
4	<i>Alopochen aegyptiaca</i>			Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)	
5	<i>Anas crecca</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)	
6	<i>Anas penelope</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Tazha	Venedikov, Gerasimov (1973)	
		Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)	Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)	
		Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)			
7	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Galabovo	Boev (2004)			
		Ratiaria	Iliev et al. (1993)			
		Sozopol	Boev (1995)			
		Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993); Boev (2006)			
		Bagachina	Boev (1996b, 1999)			
9	<i>Anas</i> sp.	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)	Garescus (pr. Sandanski)	Apollon (2012)	
10	<i>Spatula querquedula</i>	Sozopol	Boev (1995)	Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)	
		Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)			
11	<i>Plectropterus gambensis</i>			Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)	
12	<i>Anser albifrons</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Site	Bird bone remains	Source	Site	Bird images
		Serdica	Boev (2017)		Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
		Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
		Yassa-Tepe	Ribarov, Boev (1990)			
13	<i>Anser anser</i>	Galabovo	Boev (2004)			
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Ezero	Ivanov, Vasilev (1979)			
		Novae	Walushevsk-Bubien, Krupska (1983)			
		Kabile	Boev (2006)			
		Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)			
14	<i>Anser anser domestica</i>	Galabovo	Boev (2004)			
		Novae	Walushevsk-Bubien, Krupska (1983)			
15	<i>Anser erythropus</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
16	<i>Anser fabalis</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Kabile	Ribarov (1991); Boev, Ribarov (1993)		Chernozen	Kisyov (2005)
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)			
17	<i>Anser</i> sp.	Novae	Schramm (1975, 1979)			
		Bagachina	Boev (1996b, 1999)			
18	<i>Tadorna cf. tadorna</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
19	<i>Aythya ferina</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Novae	Schramm (1975)			
20	<i>Aythya nyroca</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
		Sozopol	Boev (1995)			
21	<i>Netta/ Aythya</i> sp.		Urdoviza			Boev, Ribarov (1990)
GALLIFORMES						
Phasianidae						
		Novae	Walushevsk-Bubien, Krupska (1983)			
		Armira	Boev (1999)			
		Arbanas	Boev (1997, 2006)			
22	<i>Perdix perdix</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Zelenigradska Cave	Boev (2001)			

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Bird bone remains		Bird images	
		Site	Source	Site	Source
23	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
24	<i>Alectoris graeca</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Durostorum (pr. Silistra)	Atanasov (2008)
25	<i>Alectoris chukar</i>			Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
	<i>Gallus gallus domestica</i>	Serdica	Boev (2017)	Sozopol	Gorov et al. (1967)
		Radnevo	Boev (2004)	Rila Monastery	Venedikov (1963)
		Zelenigradska Cave	Boev (2001)	Plovdiv	Martinova-Kyutova, Raycheva (2013)
		Kabile	Ribarov (1991); Boev, Ribarov (1993)		
		Chavdarova Cheshma	Boev (2017)	Oeseus	Ivanov (1955, 1957); Petrov (1986), Boev (1995)
26		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
		Ratiaria	Iliev et al. (1993)		
		Gledachevo	Boev (2006)		
		Arbanas	Boev (1997, 2006)		
		Filipovska Cave – 2	Boev (2001)		
		Abritus	Boev (2006)		
		Galabovo	Boev (2004)		
		Malak Preslavets – 2	Boev (2006)		
		Novae	Walushevska-Bubien, Krupska (1983); Schramm (1975, 1979)		
27	<i>Gallus/ Phasianus</i>	Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)		
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)		
		Sozopol	Boev (1995)		
		Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)	Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
28	<i>Phasianus colchicus</i>	Ratiaria	Iliev et al. (1993)		
		Filipovska Cave – 2	(Boev, 2001)		
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
		Galabovo	Boev (2004)		
		Kabile	Ribarov (1991)		

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Bird bone remains		Bird images	
		Site	Source	Site	Source
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Plovdiv	Martinova-Kyutova, Raycheva (2013)
29	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)		Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
		Gareus (pr. Sandanski)		Gareus (pr. Sandanski)	Apollon (2012)
		Durostorum (pr. Silistra)		Durostorum (pr. Silistra)	Atanasov (2008)
		Armira		Armira	(Plakidov, 1989)
Tetraonidae					
30	<i>Tetrao urogallus</i>	Ezero	Ivanov, Vasilev (1979)		
		Golyamata Peshtera Cave	Vasil Nikolov – unpubl. data		
Numididae					
31	<i>Numida meleagris</i>			Plovdiv	Martinova-Kyutova, Raycheva (2013)
GAVIIFORMES					
Gaviidae					
32	<i>Gavia arctica</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006)		
		Sozopol	Boev (1995)		
33	<i>Gavia arctica/stellata</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)		
34	<i>Gavia stellata</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)		
PODICIPEDIFORMES					
Podicipedidae					
35	<i>Podiceps cristatus</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
		Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)		
		Sozopol	Boev (1995)		
36	<i>Podiceps griseigena</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)		
37	<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)		

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Bird bone remains			Bird images	
		Site	Source	Site	Source	
PELECANIFORMES						
Pelecanidae						
		Novae	Bartosiewicz, Choyke (1991)			
38	<i>Pelecanus onocratalus</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
		Kostinbrod	Boev (2006)			
		Novae	Schramm (1975)			
Phalacrocoracidae						
		Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
39	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Sozopol	Boev (1995)			
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Novae	Bartosiewicz, Choyke (1991)			
40	<i>Phalacrocorax aristotelis</i>	Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
CICONIIFORMES						
Ciconiidae						
41	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>	Novae	Bartosiewicz, Choyke (1991)			
		Armira	Boev (1999)			
42	<i>Ciconia ciconia / nigra</i>	Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)			
		Ardeidae				
43	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Sozopol	Boev (1995)			
ACCIPITRIFORMES						
Pandionidae						
44	<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>			Rogozen	Fol et al. (1988)	
Accipitridae						
		Novae	Schramm (1975)			
45	<i>Accipiter gentilis</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Gledachevo	Boev (2006)			
46	<i>Accipiter nisus</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)			
47	<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	Galabovo	Boev (2004)	Morozovo (pr. Gorno Tserkovishhte)	Getov, Tsanova (1967)	

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Bird bone remains		Bird images	
		Site	Source	Site	Source
				Seuthopolis	Tsoncheva (1971)
				Shipka	Agre (2006), Marazov (2010); History Museum – Kazanlak (collection, unpubl.)
				Dragodan	Teodosiev, Manov (1993)
				Letnitsa	Venedikov (1996)
				Armira	Mladenova (1991)
				Ginina Mound, Sveshtari	Fol et al. (1986)
48	“ <i>Aquila</i> ” sp.			Nesebar	Maya Avramova (unpubl. data)
				Kabile	Regional History Museum – Yambol (unpubl.)
				Rogozen	Nikolov (1987), Nikolov et al. (1987); Marazov (1996)
				Garchimovo	Venedikov, Gerasimov (1973)
				Shekerdzha Mound, Kamen	Dimitrova (2012)
				Starosel	Kitov (2003)
49	<i>Milvus milvus</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
50	<i>Buteo buteo</i>	Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)		
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
51	cf. <i>Circus gallicus</i>	Abritus	Boev (2006)		
52	<i>Gypaetus barbatus</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
53	<i>Gyps fulvus</i>	Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)		
		Ratiaria	Iliev et al. (1993)		
54	<i>Haliaeetus albicilla</i>	Novae	Bartosiewicz, Choyke (1991)	Sofia	Mario Ivanov – unpubl. data

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Site	Bird bone remains	Source	Site	Bird images
FALCONIFORMES						
Falconidae						
55	<i>Falco cf. tinnunculus</i>	Zelenigradska Cave	Boev (2001)	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Dolna Koznitsa	Staykova (1997)
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum				
56	<i>Falco cherrug</i>	Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)		Kralevo	Ginev (1983, 2000)
57	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
STRIGIFORMES						
Strigidae						
58	<i>Athene noctua</i>	Filipovska Cave – 2	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		Malomirovo	Agre (2006); Marazov (2010)
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)			
59	<i>Strix aluco</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
		Zelenigradska Cave	Boev (2001)			
60	<i>Bubo bubo</i>	Arbanas	Boev (1997, 2006)			
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
GRUIFORMES						
Gruidae						
61	<i>Grus grus</i>	Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)		Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
		Yassa-Tepe	Ribarov, Boev (1990)			
		Novae	Bartosiewicz, Choyke (1991)			
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
Rallidae						
62	<i>Crex crex</i>	Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)			
		Urdoviza	Boev, Ribarov (1990)			
63	<i>Fulica atra</i>	Sozopol	Boev (1995)			
					Marcianopolis	Angelov (1994)
64	<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>				Garescus	Apollon (2012)
					Philippopolis	(present study)

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Site	Bird bone remains	Source	Site	Bird images	Source
OTIDIFORMES							
Otididae							
65	<i>Otis tarda</i>	Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Miramor Mound, Panagyurishte	Filov (1919)	Dzhambazov, Katincharov (1974), Gerasimova, Stoychev (1992, 1993)
66	<i>Tetrax tetrax</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Ribarov, Boev (1990)	Magurata Cave		
COLUMBIFORMES							
Columbidae							
67	<i>Columba livia</i>	Filipovska Cave – 2	(Boev, 2001)		Duvanli	Filov (1934), Venedikov (1994)	
		Arbanas	Boev (1997, 2006)				
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)		Durostorum (pr. Silistra)	Atanasov (2008)	
68	<i>Columba oenas</i>	Novae	Walushevska-Bubien, Krupska (1983)				
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)				
69	<i>Columba palumbus</i>	Ratiaria	Iliev et al. (1993)				
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)				
		Kabile	Boev, Ribarov (1993)		Galiche	Filov, Velkov (1919-1920)	
70	<i>Streptopelia turtur</i>				Orsoya	Filipov (1976); Shalganova (2005)	
					Armira	Maya Avramova (unpubl. data)	
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)				
71	<i>Treeron calva</i>				Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)	
					Sveta Sofia Church	Anonym (2014)	

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Site	Bird bone remains	Source	Site	Bird images
CAPRIMULGIFORMES						
Caprimulgidae						
72	<i>Caprimulgus europaeus</i>	Peshterata na strelite Cave Nicolopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006) Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)			
CHARADRIIFORMES						
Scolopaciidae						
73	<i>Phalaropus fulicarius</i>				Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
Laridae						
74	<i>Larus</i> sp.	Urdoviza Abritus Gledachevo	Boev, Ribarov (1990) Boev (2006) Boev (2006)		Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
PSITTACIFORMES						
Psittacidae						
75	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>				Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
76	<i>Agapornis taranta</i>				Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
CORRACHIIFORMES						
Meropidae						
77	<i>Merops apiaster</i>	Bagachina	Boev (1996b, 1999)		Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
PICIFORMES						
Picidae						
78	<i>Picus canus</i>				Philippopolis (pr. Plovdiv)	(present study)
PASSERIFORMES						
Hirundinidae						
79	<i>Hirundo daurica</i>	Filipovska Cave – 2	Boev (2001, 2006)			
Turdidae						
80	<i>Turdus merula</i>	Filipovska Cave – 2 Peshterata na strelite Cave	Boev (2001) Boev (2006)			

Table 1. Continued

No	Taxa	Bird bone remains		Bird images	
		Site	Source	Site	Source
81	<i>Turdus ruficollis</i>	Orphej	Boev (2006)		
82	<i>Erithacus rubecula</i>	Kabile	Boev (2006)		
83	<i>Turdus</i> sp.	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
Fringillidae					
84	<i>Fringilla coelebs</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)	Mogilanska Mound	Torbov (2005)
85	<i>Linaria cannabina</i>	Shipka	Boev (1996b, 1999)		
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
86	<i>Passer/Fringilla</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev, Beech (2007)		
Passeridae					
87	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
Sturnidae					
88	<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
Corvidae					
89	<i>Corvus cornix</i>	Novae	Walushevska-Bubien, Krupska (1983)		
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
90	<i>Corvus monedula</i>	Filipovska Cave – 2	Boev (2001)		
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
91	<i>Corvus</i> sp.	Filipovska Cave – 2	(Boev, 2001)		
		Novae	Schramm (1975); Walushevska-Bubien, Krupska (1983)		
92	<i>Corvus frugilegus</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
		Malak Preslavets – 2	Boev (2006)		
		Gledachevo	Boev (2006)		
93	<i>Garrulus glandarius</i>	Filipovska Cave – 2	Boev (2001)		
		Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
94	<i>Pica pica</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
95	<i>Nucifraga caryocatactes</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
		Zelenigradska Cave	Boev (2001)		
96	<i>Pyrrhocorax graculus</i>	Nicopolis-ad-Istrum	Boev (2006); Boev, Beech (2007)		
		Filipovska Cave – 2	(Boev, 2001)		
Total		84 taxa			40 taxa

Fig. 9. Ulna and two radius bones of *Pelecanus onocrotalus* from the sunken settlement of Urdiviza (3000-2000 BC.).
Photograph: Victor Hazan.

Fig. 10. Fighting roosters (domestic red junglefowl *Gallus gallus domestica*) from Ulpia Oescus (2nd c. BC). After Ivanov (1955).

Table 1 shows that in the Thracian-early-Roman time many birds have been part of the feathered game: geese, ducks, coots, bustards, grey and rock partridges, doves, grebes, pheasants, loons, etc.

Other birds (eagles, falcons, eagle owls) have been used for falconry (see below). Some (domestic chicken) have been first used for spectacular fighting (Fig. 10). Much later, they have become a preferred source of meat.

Origin of falconry in Europe in the time of ancient Thracians

A special kind of utilisation of a group of birds (diurnal and nocturnal raptors) firstly appeared during the Thracian times. According to Boev (1945), the falconry has been practiced by Thracians already in

75 BC but Simeonov (1988) states that the oldest evidence of falconry in this part of the Balkan Peninsula is from the 4th c. BC. According to Hristovich (1939), in the lands of present-day Bulgaria (in Thrace) hunting with trained diurnal raptors has been known from a later time – from the 1st c. AD.

Velkov (1956 b) gives the most detailed description of the Thracian falconers: besides for hunting mammals, the Thracians also loved to go hunting birds, using trained hawks (or falcons). This used to be particularly common practice in the downstream area of the Mesta and Struma Rivers. There, the hunters from the villages went hunting, carrying the falcons with them. Walking around the swamps, they struck the stems and surrounding bushes with sticks. The birds that were in hiding flew off, and

Fig. 11. Head of a falcon of the treasure of Kralevo (Targovishte Region; end of 4th -early 3rd c. BC). After: <https://www.google.bg/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=images&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwiZpLyJ-7TRAhXDiRoKHbKQD54QjRwIBw&url=http://www.znam.bg/com/action/showArticle?encID=1&article=792119267&psig=AFQjCNH5DQtxiUOt4gP9nDj07fcjUzFbOA&ust=1484047811958169>

Fig. 12. Eagle with a hare on a grave of Malomirovo – Zlatinitza Villages (Yambol Region; 2nd half of 4th c. c. BC). After Marazov (2010).

Fig. 14. Three ornithomorphic vessels from Orsoya (Montana Region; 14th -12th c. BC) after Bozhkov (1988).

Fig. 13. Image of a duck on a vessel from Tazha Village near the town of Kazanlak (Stara Zagora Region; 4th c. BC). After Venedikov, Gerasimov (1974).

the boys immediately released their falcons, calling them by name. The falcons rose quickly and forced the birds to return back to the bushes where the boys hunted them by striking them with sticks. Part of the hunting was handed over to the falcons. But the most interesting thing was that when they caught a bird, they did not tear it, but tossed it to the hunters (Velkov, 1956 b). Images of falcons of that period are not numerous, but some of them are of excellent

preservation (Fig. 11).

Aristotle (384-322 BC) also describes hunting of wading birds in Thrace with domesticated falcons. The hunters moved the stems of the reed with rods and the birds that were hidden in them were captured by the hunting hawks waiting for them. According to Arabadzhiev (1962), it can be concluded from the testimonies of Aristotle and Pliny the Elder (23-79 BC) that in the poleis of ancient Greece after the 6th c. BC, the hunting with trained raptors was still unknown.

Hristovich (1939) refers to Pseudo-Aristotle, who reports that in the ancient Greek city of Amphipolis, which existed from 436 BC to the 5th c. AD at the mouth of the Struma River, the hunting of grey partridges (*Perdix perdix*) with trained

Fig. 15. Eagle from a mound burial near Dragodan Village (Kyustendil Region; 2nd c. BC). After Teodosiev, Manov (1993).

Fig. 16. Eagle statuettes of the necropolis near Dolna Koznitsa Village (Kyustendil Region; 4th c. BC). After Staykova (1997).

falcons was spread. It is believed that the Thracians hunted with trained hawks and falcons 2200 years ago (Arabadzhev, 1962, Denkov, 1988). Numerous are the images also of the precisely dated Thracian silver objects representing hunting of hares with eagles/falcons (Rogozen – Nikolov, 1987; Malomirovo – Agre, 2006), which confirms such a view.

It is supposed that the falconry, an aristocratic way of hunting, has been re-transferred to Europe from the eastern Roman provinces no later than the beginning of the 1st c. AD. It is well known that the Roman Emperor Avitus (ca. 450 AD) introduced hunting with trained falcons in order to entertain the Emperor's Court (Arabadzhev, 1962).

Although the falconry is known in the ancient Rome, reliable information on this practice during the Roman rule (168 BC – 3rd c. AD) in today's Bulgarian lands is still missing.

An eagle holding a hare with its claws is depicted on a greave from a grave between the Malomirovo and Zlatinitsa Villages (Fig. 12).

Bird images on the objects of the Thracian art

According to Lazarov (1990), in the 7th -5th c. BC (the "archaic" period of the Thracian art), the subjects are expanding, along with bulls, deer, boars, goats, eagles, cocks and water birds found in the

earlier period, at that time have appeared also lions, panthers, and dogs. As before, animals are usually displayed on a profile. Bowls with the image of birds, best testified again in Istria (in the westernmost part of the Balkan Peninsula), are also common in Eastern Thrace (Thracia Pontica). There are many animal figures represented in the Pontic pottery: deer, wild boars, panthers, lions, waterfowl (Fig. 13). The Corinthian painted pottery abounds with fantastic creatures and monsters: sirens, sphinxes, wings of dragons (Lazarov, 1990).

In hinterland Thrace birds are also present in the items of treasures, e.g. the Rogozen treasure in ornaments and palmettes alternating with stylised birds. The birds' heads are turned backwards (Fol et al. (1988).

In the vicinities of the Drama and Zavoy Villages (Yambol Region) have been found excellent examples of the s. c. "bird bowls" of the Early Iron Age/ the beginning of the Late Iron Age (second quarter – end of 7th c. BC; Karadzhev, 2012). The author concludes that they are known from "several sites in the Pontic Area, concentrated along the Northern Black Sea coast and the Northern Anatolian hinterland" (p. 10).

It is known, that the "bird bowls" have been produced in special bird bowls workshops in the

Fig. 17. Silhouette of an eagle from Mesembria (pr. Nesebar, Burgas Region; 3rd c. BC). After Maya Avramova (unpubl.).

Fig. 18. Osprey of the Rogozen treasure (Rogozen Village, Vratsa Region; 2nd half of 4th c. BC). After Marazov (1996).

Fig. 19. Osprey from the Vratsa treasure (Vratsa Region; 2nd half of 4th c. BC). After Torbov (2005).

Fig. 20. Image of a "pigeon" from Mushovitsa mound, Duvanli Village (Plovdiv Region; 5th c. BC). After Venedikov (1994).

Northern Ionia in the 2nd quarter of the 7th to the 1st decades of the 5th c. BC. (Karadzhinov, 2012).

The bird motifs are widely spread in the art of the Bronze Age and Early Iron Age in the central parts of the Balkan Peninsula (Vasic, Vasic, 2000). In Eastern Serbia, for example, numerous bird-chariots, bird-vases, bird-rattles, bird-pendants, bird-fibulae, etc. have been found. Waterfowl (ducks) are the most often depicted. Vasic and Vasic (2000) defined a special cult of ducks as peaceful dwellers of water bodies close to human settlements. The excellent ceramic ornithomorphic vessels from Orsoya near the town of Lom in NW Bulgaria are of the same type (Fig. 14). Filipov (1976) also concludes that in the late Bronze Age the ornithomorphic vessels are inherent in the culture of inlaid ceramics on the Lower Danube River. They are found mostly in the necropoles. There are also a number of other ceramic ornithomorphic cult objects as chariot models, labs, thrones, tables, anthropomorphic idols, etc.

The images of the "eagle" and the "osprey"

It is broadly accepted that the "eagle" is a symbol of "the supreme authority in the Iranian-Caucasian world" (Todorova et al., 2011) and among the Scythians (Melyukova, Moshkova, 1976). The image of the "eagle" is present in the Thracian art in the Late Iron Age tomb architecture – Sveshtari (Pavlov, 1982, Golemanov, 2012), toreutics – the treasures of Letnitsa (Nikolov, 1974), Lukovit (Chichikova, 1980), Starosel (Kitov, 2003), Borovo (Ivanov, 1975), Rogozen (Nikolov et al., 1987; Fol et al., 1988), some other finds (from Stara Zagora /Venedikov, 1974a/) (Figs. 15-17).

The image of the "eagle" is the most often depicted bird image. Images of "eagle" are common in the Thracian art, as those of lions (Golemanov, 2012).

Another "eagle", the fish-eating osprey (*Pandion haliaetus*), is very probably depicted on a vessel of the Rogozen treasure (Fol et al., 1988, p. 146; Figs. 18-19). Not only the beaked fish, but some details of the image (distinctive separation between head and neck and its shape, the beak shape /and its smaller size/, the eye-ring, etc.) suggest for an image of osprey.

The images of the "pigeon" and the "dove"

The pigeons are an ornithomorphic metaphor of the lasses, while the cut wings of the birds symbolise their lost virginity (Marazov, 2016). Their images are often present on the Thracian (and later Roman) monuments (Fig. 20).

Roman-Ethiopian influence on the depicted bird fauna of the Roman Bishop Basilica in Plovdiv (Roman Philippopolis)

The exotic birds of the Roman Bishop Basilica

Fig. 21. Present range of purple swamphen (*Porphyrio porphyrio*) and the territory of the Roman Empire at the time of its height in 117 AD. (After BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2017 and Anonym (2018).

Fig. 22. Present range of Egyptian goose (*Alopochen aegyptiaca*) and the territory of the Roman Empire at the time of its height in 117 AD. (After BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2017 and Anonym (2018).

Fig. 23. Present range of ring-necked parakeet (*Psittacula krameri*) and the territory of the Roman Empire at the time of its height in 117 AD. (After BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2017 and Anonym (2018).

Fig. 24. Present range of helmeted guineafowl (*Numida meleagris*) and the territory of the Roman Empire at the time of its height in 117 AD. (After BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2017 and Anonym (2018).

Fig. 25. Present range of Abyssinian lovebird (*Agapornis taranta*) and the territory of the Roman Empire at the time of its height in 117 AD. (After BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2017 and Anonym (2018).

Fig. 26. Present range of African green pigeon (*Treron calvus*) and the territory of the Roman Empire at the time of its height in 117 AD. (After BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2017 and Anonym (2018).

Fig. 27. Present range of spur-winged goose (*Plectropterus gambiensis*) and the territory of the Roman Empire at the time of its height in 117 AD. (After BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2017 and Anonym (2018).

in Plovdiv are alien to the recent Bulgarian fauna: Purple swamphen (Fig. 21), Egyptian goose (Fig. 22), ring-necked parakeet (Fig. 23), helmeted guineafowl (Fig. 24), Abyssinian lovebird (Fig. 25), African green pigeon (Fig. 26), spur-winged goose (Fig. 27; Table 2). These exotic bird species comprise 1/3 of all recorded species of birds (including domestic forms as peafowl and chicken) among the mosaics of this remarkable monument of ancient art. Seven of the 20 recognised bird species/forms, are exotic as compared to present day fauna, mainly inhabiting Northern and Sub-Saharan Africa. These birds have unmistakable coloration of their plumage (and habitus in general) and unquestionably prove the ancient contacts of the Romans far southward, beyond the broadly-accepted borders of the Roman Empire.

A striking fact: All exotic birds of the Bishop Basilica (except for the domestic peafowl) at present are spread in East Africa: Ethiopia, Eritrea and South Sudan. This region has remained beyond the most south-eastern limits of the Roman Empire even in its height in 117 AD and lies at circa 1000 km away from the former Roman lands. At present, all these exotic birds (except *N. meleagris* and *P. porphyrio*) have Sub-Saharan ranges (Figs. 22-27). Besides in Sub-Saharan Africa, *N. meleagris* is spread also in

Morocco (Martinez, 1994) and *P. porphyrio* occurs also in Southern Spain, France, Italy, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, Egypt and Iran (Taylor, 1996). All these territories were part of the Roman Empire.

The occurrence of the helmeted guineafowl (Fig. 28) needs special attention. According to Larson, Fuller (2014), *N. meleagris* occurs naturally in the wild through Sub-Saharan Africa, but numerous artistic and bone evidence suggests it may have been domesticated in Mali and Sudan about 2000 ago. In Europe probably it became “extinct” in captivity and the species was secondarily domesticated (again in Europe) in the 16th c. AD after Portuguese travels in the region of W Africa (Sossinka, 1982).

The complete aridisation of Sahara finished by 3500 BC (Capot-Rey, 1958). Additionally, the most extensive expansion of the Sahara Desert occurred in the last two millennia (Cloudsley-Thompson, 1990). As a result, the climate of North Africa has not changed tangibly since the Roman colonisation (Capot-Rey, 1958). Thus, the northern range limits of some present-day “Sub-Saharan” species of birds, could be much more extended northward, reaching the south-eastern corner of the Roman Empire.

On the other hand, there are a number of evi-

Table 2. Mosaic images of birds from the of Bishop Basilica of Philippopolis – pr. Plovdiv

No	Species	Mosaic images	
ANSERIFORMES			
Anatidae			
1	<i>Alopochen aegyptiaca</i>	A mosaic depicting a duck, likely an Egyptian duck (Alopochen aegyptiaca), shown in profile facing left. The bird is rendered in shades of brown, tan, and white, with a long neck and a slightly upturned bill. The mosaic is set against a background of light-colored tesserae.	
2	<i>Anas crecca</i>	A mosaic of a mallard duck (Anas crecca) shown in profile facing left. The duck has a distinctive blue-green head and neck, a brown body, and a long, slightly upturned bill. The mosaic is set within a square frame of light-colored tesserae.	
3	<i>Spatula querquedula</i>	A mosaic of a tufted duck (Spatula querquedula) shown in profile facing left. The duck has a brown head and neck, a dark body, and a long, slightly upturned bill. The mosaic is set against a background of light-colored tesserae with some floral motifs.	
4	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	A mosaic of a mallard duck (Anas platyrhynchos) shown in profile facing left. The duck has a blue-green head and neck, a brown body, and a long, slightly upturned bill. The mosaic is set against a background of light-colored tesserae.	

No	Species	Mosaic images	
5	<i>Anser anser</i>		
6	<i>Plectropterus gambensis</i>		
Galliformes			
Phasianidae			
7	<i>Gallus gallus domestica</i> – male		
	<i>Gallus gallus domestica</i> – male		

No	Species	Mosaic images	
5	<i>Phasianus colchicus</i> – female	A circular mosaic depicting a female Phasianus colchicus (Pheasant) in profile, facing right. The bird has a reddish-brown body and a long, patterned tail. The mosaic is set within a circular frame of small, light-colored tiles.	
	<i>Phasianus colchicus</i> – male	A rectangular mosaic depicting a male Phasianus colchicus (Pheasant) in profile, facing left. The bird has a reddish-brown body and a long, patterned tail. The mosaic is set within a rectangular frame of small, light-colored tiles.	
	<i>Phasianus colchicus</i> – male	A rectangular mosaic depicting a male Phasianus colchicus (Pheasant) in profile, facing left. The bird has a reddish-brown body and a long, patterned tail. The mosaic is set within a rectangular frame of small, light-colored tiles.	
6	<i>Alectoris chukar</i>	A rectangular mosaic depicting a quail (Alectoris chukar) in profile, facing left. The bird has a brown body and a long, patterned tail. The mosaic is set within a rectangular frame of small, light-colored tiles.	
7	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	A rectangular mosaic depicting a quail (Coturnix coturnix) in profile, facing left. The bird has a brown body and a long, patterned tail. The mosaic is set within a rectangular frame of small, light-colored tiles.	

No	Species	Mosaic images	
8	<i>Pavo cristatus</i> – male		
	<i>Pavo cristatus</i> – male		
Numididae			
9	<i>Numida meleagris</i>		
GRUIFORMES			
Gruidae			
10	<i>Grus grus</i>		

No	Species	Mosaic images	
Rallidae			
11	<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>		
	<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>		
	<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>		
	<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>		
CHARADRIIFORMES			
Scolopacidae			
12	<i>Phalaropus fulicarius</i>		

No	Species	Mosaic images	
Laridae			
13	<i>Larus sp.</i>		
PICIFORMES			
Picidae			
14	<i>Picus canus</i>		
PSITTACIFORMES			
Psittacidae			
15	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>		
	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>		

No	Species	Mosaic images	
16	<i>Agapornis taranta</i>		
COLUMBIFORMES			
Columbidae			
17	<i>Treron calva</i>		

dences confirming trans-Saharan commercial ties of the Roman Empire at least since the 3rd c. BC (Capot-Rey, 1958). After the rule of the emperor Augustus (63 BC-14 AD), Rome had four provinces in Africa: Numidia, Africa (Tunisia), Cyrenaica and Egypt (Swanson, 1972).

All this facts unequivocally confirm the Roman-Ethiopian/Abyssinian contacts. It is worthy to mention, that the contacts between Ethiopia and the Mediterranean World (3000 BC – 400 AD) were numerous and intensive, as has been proved by Swanson (1972). The author states that the contacts between the Roman world and Ethiopia date between 50 BC and 300 AD, when Rome began to expand onto the African continent. Romans had contacts with the State of Kush, the Ethiopian Kingdom (750 BC to 200 AD). The Kushites and their successors were often militarily and commercially involved with Rome and these interrelationships were of some importance during the lifetime of the Roman Empire

(Swanson, 1972: p. 4). They were most intensive in the period of 50 BC to 300 AD. “What was the trade that went on between Rome and Ethiopia over the Saharan trails? It certainly involved animals – the vast quantities of exotic species that were slaughtered in the arenas of Rome were usually of Ethiopian origin, brought up from Central Africa via the Sahara and the Fezzan.” (Swanson, 1972: p. 28). Hence, the lands of pr. Ethiopia and Sudan were the major source of animals for the Roman arenas. According the numerous evidences, the Ethiopian Kush Kingdom have exported to Rome (i. e. Egypt in that time) “... traditional products of the caravan trade, as ivory, gold, wild beasts, spices and slaves” (Swanson, 1972: p. 66). Numerous are the historical evidences for the ancient contacts between Thrace and Egypt in the Hellenic epoch, especially in the region between the Lower Nile River and the Red Sea (Atanasova, 2017).

Thus, in Central Sahara the contacts between the Mediterranean world and Ethiopia were es-

entially trade contacts. These contacts were quite extensive. Trade by its very nature is a contact between peoples and, although direct physical contact between Romans and Sub-Saharan Ethiopians was probably limited, there is no doubt that the trans-Saharan trade was important to the classical world” (Swanson, 1972: p. 29).

While the large mammals of the Ethiopian region have been supplied into the Roman Empire for slaughtering in the arenas, the presence of the colourful birds (all of them non-passerine), which are found in the Roman mosaics in Philippopolis, could only be explained by their aesthetic value, such as bright colour plumage, amazing behaviour, beautiful plumage ornamentation, etc. All these exotic for Bulgaria birds of African (Ethiopian) origin could not be depicted without direct observation of live individuals. That means (and proves) that live individuals of the seven exotic birds (purple swamphen, Egyptian goose, ring-necked parakeet, helmeted guineafowl, Abyssinian lovebird, African green pigeon, and spur-winged goose) have been brought in the ancient Philippopolis and pictured as (basic) elements of the floor mosaic decoration of the Bishop Basilica. Mosaic images of the purple swamphen exist in another Roman town, Marcianopolis (pr. Devnya; Boev, 1997b) and the Thracian town Garescus (pr. Sandanski; Apollon, 2012). Roman mosaics of Indian peafowl are known in Garescus, Marcianopolis, etc. (Table. 1). Other birds are mentioned among the images of the mosaic in Sandanski (Plakidov, 1989), St. Sofia Basilica (Fig. 29), etc.

Plakidov (1989) gives the most synthetic overview of the animalistic subjects in the Roman mosaics: The hunting theme treated in the Roman floor mosaics expresses the assertive life understanding. There is no hint of any cruelty, nor killing of the game. On the contrary, animal figures are radiating the immense feeling of artist's sympathy. Here dominate the friendship and the beauty. Perhaps this is due to the ancients' conviction of the indivisibility of nature, of its unity, in which both game and hunter constitute a harmonious whole.

Discussion and Conclusion

Birds have played an important role both in the everyday and spiritual life of the people in the Thracian/Roman period and, thus are well presented in the ancient Thracian and Roman art. Usually the Thracian images were symbolic, generalised and stylised and they often lacked important specific diagnostic features for species identification.

In the Roman period bird images were much more realistic. Their specific features were ingen-

Fig. 28. Helmeted guineafowl (*Numida meleagris*) from the Roman mosaic of the Bishop Basilica in Plovdiv (5-6th c. BC). After: https://www.google.bg/search?q=%D0%B5%D0%BF%D0%B8%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BF%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%B0+%D0%B1%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%B8%D0%BA%D0%B0+%D0%BF%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B4%D0%B8%D0%B2&dcr=0&source=lnms&tbm=isch&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwiW67_zhb7ZAhXLzaQKHfh8AdwQAUCigB&biw=1920&bih=888#imgsrc=O1M5s7RWG6asEM:&spf=1519457936392

Fig. 29. Pigeons (? *Columba livia*). Mosaics of the St. Sofia Basilica 4th c. AD; Sofia). After: <http://www.google.bg/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=images&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwjTzPDu9vLYAhVQb1AKHXLLCXIQjRwLBw&url=http://crhc-sofia.com/bg/content/podovamozayka-rayat&psig=AOvVaw2kSZ-zs9cGnO3Q72ccoWN-&ust=1516962853937981>

iously stylised, but sufficiently preserved for reliable taxonomic identification (Table 2).

Most of the depicted bird species of the Roman mosaics are native and are spread in Bulgaria at present. Although some of them are not breeding in the country, they are still represented in the nature of the present Bulgarian territory as occasional or regular winter visitors: common crane, Colchic pheasant

(wild native, not the hybridised from), grey phalarope. The common crane disappeared as a nesting species in the 1950s, while the native Colchic pheasant survived until the early 1990s. The grey Phalarope is an extremely rare winter visitor. On the other hand, the common quail, grey-headed woodpecker, chukar partridge, garganey, mallard, common teal and the graylag goose occur and breed throughout the country.

In general, hunting birds were rarely depicted, except those with colourful decorative (or specific contrast) plumage, e. g. the chukar partridge, mute swan, helmeted guineafowl, mallard, etc.

Other of the recorded birds on various monuments were used as pets (parrots, Indian peafowl, chicken, purple swamphen). Some of them are a traditional source of meat and subject of poultry breeding (chicken, Indian peafowl, helmeted guineafowl, geese and ducks).

The precise colourful images of birds in the floor mosaics of the Roman Bishop Basilica in Philippopolis (pr.** Plovdiv) are so realistic that Bulgarian Government deposited in 2017 an official application for their recognition as part of the World Cultural Heritage of UNESCO (Chaleva, 2017). They represent a rare proof for the ancient Roman-Ethiopian interrelations.

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** pr. – present

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